

**INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**
[ISSN: 0975-4725; CODEN(USA): IJPS00]
Journal Homepage: <https://www.ijpsjournal.com>

Case Study

Methotrexate Induced Oral Ulcers in an Elderly Patient with Rheumatoid Arthritis and Comorbidities: A Sporadic Case Report

Rishika S.*, Reshma Babu, Shaiju Dharan

Department of Pharmacy Practice, Ezhuthachan College of Pharmaceutical Sciences, Marayamuttom, Thiruvananthapuram, Kerala, India 695124.

ARTICLE INFO

Published: 09 Apr 2026

Keywords:

Methotrexate toxicity, oral ulcers, rheumatoid arthritis, elderly patient, dosing error, leucovorin rescue

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.19480583

ABSTRACT

Methotrexate is a widely used disease-modifying antirheumatic drug (DMARD) in the treatment of rheumatoid arthritis due to its immunosuppressive and anti-inflammatory properties. However, inappropriate dosing can result in severe toxicity. This article propose a clinically relevant case of MTX toxicity complicated by oral ulcers, highlighting the need for clear communication between doctors, patients and caregivers regarding duration and dosage, especially in older adults on using complex treatment regimens. MTX is commonly prescribed for RA and Psoriasis, as well as in cancer treatment. However, inappropriate use may result in severe adverse effects such as GI issues (nausea, vomiting, diarrhea, oral ulcers), hepatotoxicity, pulmonary toxicity, nephrotoxicity and bone marrow suppression. We present the case of a 68-year-old women presented with the history of seropositive RA, systemic hypertension, and prediabetes, who had found to have ulcer-oral cavity and systemic symptoms due to an inadvertent overdose of MTX daily for 5 consecutive days by her caregiver. Dermatology evaluation confirmed MTX induced oral ulcers. She was promptly treated with Leucovorin (a methotrexate antidote), fluids, antibiotics, steroids, and oral care. Within few days her condition was gradually started to improve. This case reminds the need for careful monitoring of MTX dosing schedule by educating not only the patient but also the families and ensuring regular follow-up can help prevent such avoidable yet dangerous medication errors.

INTRODUCTION

Methotrexate (MTX) comes under the category of biological disease-modifying antirheumatic drugs

(DMARDs), which was initially developed in 1948 and indicated to treat neoplastic diseases and psoriasis; later it was identified to treat rheumatoid arthritis (RA) in 1980 and became the first-line

*Corresponding Author: Rishika S.

Address: Department of Pharmacy Practice, Ezhuthachan College of Pharmaceutical Sciences, Marayamuttom, Thiruvananthapuram, Kerala, India 695124.

Email ✉: rishikax33@gmail.com

Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

therapy among the DMARDs in 1990. The well-known mechanism of MTX; it with inhibit the enzyme responsible for converting dihydrofolates to tetrahydrofolates; the enzyme is dihydrofolate reductase (DHFR); additionally it will also inhibits the TYMS and AICAR formyl-transferase. MTX is most popularly known for its immunosuppressive and anti-inflammatory properties [1]. Nonetheless, MTX is a relatively low-efficacy (20mg) therapeutic. Incidentally, when dosing errors happen — which are common especially in patients who are elderly and have comorbidities or renal impairment; toxicity may be severe. Mouth ulcers, bone marrow suppression, gastrointestinal upset, liver dysfunction and rarely lung and kidney injury have been reported as adverse effects [2]. Impaired renal clearance in the elderlies increased the risk further, and therefore dose adjustment should be particularly careful with a regular monitoring [3]. The painful ulcerations in the mouth and GI tract reflect the effect that MTX toxicity has on rapid turnover of epithelial cells, leading to oral mucosal injury. One mistake that can arise is when MTX intended for once-weekly dosage gets taken daily very often through self-administration or by misinformed caregivers, but sometimes also in the setting of impaired renal function with skipped folic acid

supplementation. This is supported by several case reports in which patients inadvertently ingested low-dose MTX daily and noted mild early symptoms including mucosal ulcers, nausea, diarrhea and pancytopenia; these more commonly preceded major complications such as bone marrow suppression or multi-organ failure. Recognition of these complications and immediate intervention can dramatically change the course [4]. The cornerstone therapy in MTX toxicity is leucovorin (folinic acid) rescue, which helps restore folate-dependent cellular processes and ease damage, alongside measures such as intravenous fluids, electrolyte correction and temporarily discontinuing MTX. With appropriate and immediate treatment, oral ulcers often heal, blood counts become normal and systemic symptoms resolve [5]. This article aims to present a clinically relevant case of MTX toxicity complicated by oral ulcers, highlighting the need for prudent use of MTX and bracing the importance of communication about dosing schedules, to verify patient understanding and to involve caregivers in the education process when appropriate. Through this case, we prioritize the importance of preventive education and vigilant in monitoring adverse effects associated with oral therapy [6].

4-Amino-N¹⁰-methyl-pteroylglutamic acid

Case Report

A 68-years-old female patient was admitted to the General Medicine Department with the complaints of ulcer-oral cavity, right leg ulcer, left knee pain and bilateral foot pain. The patient had a past medical history of Systemic Hypertension-

managed with TAB. TELMISARTAN 40mg P/O 1-0-0 and she was diagnosed with RA (predominant Lower limb symptoms) 5 months ago, since then she had been managed with TAB. HYDROXYCHLOROQUINE 300mg 0-0-1, TAB. METHYLPREDNISOLONE 4mg 1-0-0, TAB. CALCIUM CITRATE + VITAMIN D3 +

ZINC SULFATE + MAGNESIUM SULPHATE 1000mg + 200IU + 4mg + 100mg 1-0-0, TAB. RABEPRAZOLE + DOMPERIDONE 20mg+10mg 1-0-0, TAB. ETORICOXIB 90mg 0-0-1, TAB. PREDNISOLONE 10mg 1-0-1 for 2 weeks and 1-0-0 for next 2 weeks, TAB. FOLIC ACID 5mg twice weekly, TAB. METHOTREXATE 20mg intended for once

weekly which she has been taken everyday for 5 days, which was given to her by the bystander.

The patient was conscious, heart sounds were heard, chest was clear, was able to move all limbs, and GI series showed no abnormalities. During admission, she had a Pulse Rate of 88 beats/min, Respiratory Rate of 24 breaths/min, Blood Pressure of 130/70mmHg.

Table 1(a): Laboratory Investigation – Elevated Parameters

PARAMETERS	TEST VALUE
ESR	60mm/hr
HbA1C	6.1%
Urea	50mg/dL
CRP	49.1mg/L

Table 1(b): Laboratory Investigation – Declined Parameters

PARAMETERS	TEST VALUES
Hb	10.8g/dL
PCV	32.7%
WBC Count	3640cells/mm ³
Polymorphs	38.5%
Lymphocytes	55.5%
Monocytes	0.5%
Sodium	134mEq/L
Serum Methotrexate	<0.04µmol/L

Arterial doppler study of right and left lower limb showed, diffuse atherosclerotic changes in the form of intimo medial thickening and luminal irregularity in right lower limb and left lower limb arteries showing no hemodynamic stenosis/occlusion. Venous doppler study of right and left lower limb showed, no deep venous thrombosis in right lower limb and left lower limb (Figure 1).Initially Dermatology consultation was done and withheld the TAB. METHOTREXATE, validated the intervention and diagnosed as METHOTREXATE toxicity-induced oral ulcer and advised with INJ. LEUCOVORIN CALCIUM (an antidote to MTX toxicity) 50mg with 100ml NORMAL SALINE IV over 2 hours as stat given

initially and then converted to 25mg IV Q6H for the next two days, CHLORHEXIDINE MOUTH WASH L/A 1-1-1, METRONIDAZOLE ORAL GEL L/A BD, TRIAMCINOLONE ACETONIDE BUCCAL PASTE L/A 1-0-1, LIOVIN CREAM L/A BD for treating hyperpigmentation in the leg. General Surgery consultation was done in view of right leg ulcer, venous doppler had been taken, no DVT and advised with TAB. COUMARIN 200mg P/O 1-0-1, TAB. VERICOLYTE FORTE P/O 1-0-1. Other supportive measures were INJ. HYDROCORTISONE 50mg IV BD to control systemic inflammation, INJ. PIPERACILLIN + TAZOBACTAM 4.5g IV TID for treating infection conditions, SYP. SUCRALFATE +

OXETACAINE 10mL P/O 1-1-1 for gastric mucosal protection, TAB. TELMISARTAN 40mg P/O 1-0-0 for treating systemic hypertension, INJ. BIPHASIC INSULIN S/C 14 UNIT 0-0-1 to treat prediabetes, NORMAL SALINE INFUSION 500ml along with INJ. SODIUM BICARBONATE 3 AMPOULES to eliminate MTX through urine by alkalinizing the urine. After 4 days of admission patient got symptomatically better, laboratory parameters are gradually returned back to normal and was discharged with

TAB. PREDNISOLONE 10mg P/O 1-0-0, TRIAMCINOLONE ACETONIDE BUCCAL PASTE L/A 1-0-1, TAB. FOLIC ACID 10mg P/O 1-0-0, CHLORHEXIDINE MOUTH WASH L/A 1-1-1, TAB. TELMISARTAN 40mg P/O 1-0-0, TAB. COUMARIN P/O 200mg 1-0-1, TAB.VERICOLYTE FORTE P/O 1-0-1, METRONIDAZOLE ORAL GEL L/A BD, LIOVIN CREAM L/A BD, TAB. HYDROXYCHLOROQUINE 200mg P/O 0-0-1.

Figure 1 : Doppler Study

DISCUSSION

Methotrexate has recently become the mostly used drug treatment for disorders like psoriasis and rheumatoid arthritis-used as low dose, once a week therapy. It is used because of its immunosuppressive and anti-inflammatory properties. However, inappropriate dosing of even low dose MTX can lead to serious but reversible side effects; the most common is oral ulcers-reported in most of the clinical trials which are encountered by dental practitioners [7]. In this case, the patient's unintended daily intake of low-dose Methotrexate had led to Methotrexate toxicity

induced oral ulcers. In elderly patients with multiple comorbidities such medication errors are noted when the caregivers misunderstand the dosing regimens. Methotrexate toxicity cases observed from daily rather than weekly dosing in older age has confirmed in a retrospective observational study conducted on non-oncologic outpatients [8]. Likewise, Dorji et al., in a clinical study with similar case reports had observed, early mucocutaneous toxicity with painful mucositis which has been identified as a sentinel warning sign [9].

Comparison with other Case Reports

The results in this instance align with multiple previously documented cases of methotrexate toxicity, especially those associated with dosing mistakes. In a recent series by Dugad et al., the majority of patients who experienced toxicity had incorrectly taken methotrexate every day instead of weekly, akin to the current case. Oral ulcers were noted as a common initial sign, frequently occurring before more severe issues like pancytopenia ^[10]. This aligns closely with our patient, where mucositis served as the initial clinical warning sign. Likewise, Schelzel et al., reported on an elderly individual receiving low-dose methotrexate who exhibited painful oral lesions and blood-related issues. The research highlighted that even typical doses can result in serious toxicity when extra risk factors like kidney dysfunction or older age are involved ^[11]. In contrast, our case illustrates how a medication error by itself, even in the absence of considerable comorbid decline, can lead to toxicity.

Prognosis

The patient had a positive outlook primarily because of the swift identification of methotrexate toxicity and the quick start of suitable treatment. After discontinuing the problematic medication and administering supportive treatment, such as leucovorin rescue, the patient demonstrated consistent clinical progress. The mouth sores started to heal slowly and related symptoms diminished after a few days. No lasting complications were detected throughout the recovery period. This case indicates that if detected early, methotrexate induced toxicity especially affecting the mucosa can be successfully reversed through suitable intervention and careful observation.

CONCLUSION

This case underlines how a frequently prescribed medication can cause serious damage when dosage guidelines are misinterpreted. The onset of oral ulcers acted as an early indicator of underlying toxicity and facilitated the prompt initiation of treatment. More significantly, it highlights a preventable issue medication mistakes. Effective communication, adequate counselling and the engagement of caregivers are essential in promoting safe medication use, particularly in elderly individuals undergoing long-term treatment. Enhancing these elements in everyday clinical practice can significantly help minimize preventable adverse drug reactions and boost patient safety.

Patient Consent

The complete written informed consent was obtained from patient and by stander for the publication in this study.

REFERENCES

1. Restrepo LF, Giraldo R, Londoño J, Pinzón C, Cortes A, Ballesteros G, Santos AM. Pharmacogenetics of methotrexate in rheumatoid arthritis: a systematic review. *Revista Colombiana de Reumatología (English Edition)*. 2016 Apr 1;23(2):102-14.
2. Hanoodi M, Mittal M. Methotrexate. InStatPearls [Internet] 2024 Dec 11. StatPearls Publishing.
3. Tett SE, Triggs EJ. Use of methotrexate in older patients: a risk-benefit assessment. *Drugs & aging*. 1996 Dec;9(6):458-71.
4. Davey E, Isbister GK. Repeated daily dosing of weekly methotrexate therapy causing multiorgan toxicity: a case report. *Toxicology Communications*. 2023 Dec 31;7(1):2221508.
5. Bhargava M, Kopp CR, Naidu S, Dhivar DP, Saroch A, Khadwal A, Narang T, Jain S, Khullar A, Leishangthem B, Sharma A.

- Comparison of two doses of leucovorin in severe low-dose methotrexate toxicity—a randomized controlled trial. *Arthritis Research & Therapy*. 2023 May 19;25(1):82.
6. Dorji T, Penjor T, Tenzin S, Pedon T, Wangchuck S, Yangchen S. Mucocutaneous Ulcerations and Pancytopenia Secondary to Methotrexate Toxicity in a Patient With Rheumatoid Arthritis: A Case Report. *Clinical Case Reports*. 2024 Dec;12(12):e9638.
 7. Deeming GM, Collingwood J, Pemberton MN. Methotrexate and oral ulceration. *British dental journal*. 2005 Jan;198(2):83-5.
 8. Chamorro-Petronacci C, García-García A, Lorenzo-Pouso AI, Gómez-García FJ, Padín-Iruegas ME, Gándara-Vila P, Blanco-Carrión A, Pérez-Sayáns M. Management options for low-dose methotrexate-induced oral ulcers: A systematic review. *Medicina oral, patologia oral y cirugía bucal*. 2019 Mar;24(2):e181.
 9. Kalantzis A, Marshman Z, Falconer DT, Morgan PR, Odell EW. Oral effects of low-dose methotrexate treatment. *Oral Surgery, Oral Medicine, Oral Pathology, Oral Radiology, and Endodontology*. 2005 Jul 1;100(1):52-62.
 10. Dugad A, Shaik MH, Patil R, Vikhe V, Desai I. A Case series of Acute Methotrexate Toxicity. *Ann Afr Med*. 2026 Jan 23. French, English. doi: 10.4103/aam.aam_431_25. Epub ahead of print.
 11. Schelzel G, Palicherla A, Tauseef A, Millner P. Low-dose methotrexate toxicity leading to pancytopenia: leucovorin as a rescue treatment. *Proc (Bayl Univ Med Cent)*. 2024;37(2):339–343.

HOW TO CITE: Rishika S., Reshma Babu, Shaiju Dharan, Methotrexate Induced Oral Ulcers in an Elderly Patient with Rheumatoid Arthritis and Comorbidities: A Sporadic Case Report, *Int. J. of Pharm. Sci.*, 2026, Vol 4, Issue 4, 1443-1448, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19480583>

